

De-Radicalization for Pakistan Specially The Role of Youth In Promoting Peace and Tolerance

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Abstract

"Acknowledgement ,tolerance and pardon .these are lessons for whole life ."Jessica Lange .(1) Radicalization is the mother of terrorism and extremism .Pakistan is a heterogeneous society with the sense of lack of patriotism since at the time of birth. Today,s society is crisis - ridden . The issue of terrorism .sectarian violence .extremism and insurgencies are the formidable challenges . The external and internal interference is key component to disrupt the Pakistani state . The radicalization is ingrained in roots of Pakistani society and it is reflected in foreign policy. The de-radicalization is really essential for Pakistani society .The 9/11 event is a turning point in the history of Muslim world ,and it leded towards engulfing the gap between Muslim and western world .The issue of terrorism . sectarian violence and extremism are very sensitive and are flare up due to external and internal factors .The option of war is not a solution of terrorism There is a need of a socio- political strategy to eradicate the extremism at every level of society . The qualitative and descriptive research methodology will be applied in this research paper .The primary source interviews from youth and secondary sources i.e. books journals and magazines etc. .will be used .The religious-political approach will be adopted to assess the issues of radicalization and how to switch over towards peace and tolerance in a state . The various research questions will the part of research design .The objective of this research paper are that to highlight the causes of radicalization in Pakistan ,and deradicalisation is essential for the promotion of peace and tolerance in Pakistan . Apart from this ,to assess the role of youth for the promotion of peace and tolerance in Pakistan . Youth are the ambassadors of the state for the sake of promotion of peace .The youth involvement is essential to promote peace and security in the world .Islam is the religion of peace and security .Holy Prophet laid down the real example of tolerance. This research paper will deal that what type of strategy should be adopted to radicalize the state of Pakistan by probing the all possible internal and external factors . What types of steps should taken by youth as a change agent to promote peace and tolerance in Pakistani society .In the last, the results , discussions and original findings based on research about that how radicalization has been seeped in Pakistani society and what are counter measures to eradicate it. What are missions ,goal ,vision and practical to radicalize this state by promoting the peace and tolerance .

Keywords: Radicalization, Extremism, Tolerance, peace. Role of Youth.

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